

Attitude of Secondary School Teachers towards Equitable Education in Coimbatore District

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Thus, education is not only an instrument of enhancing efficiency but is also an effective tool for widening and augmenting democratic participation and upgrading the overall quality of individual and societal life (Goel, 2008). It plays a significant role in the progress of an individual and country.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"ATTITUDE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS EQUITABLE EDUCATION IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT"

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Baldwin and James (2015) conducted a study on International patterns in access to higher education and the complex issues surrounding equity and social imbalances in access to higher education. To identify contemporary research questions, including the reasons for the apparent failure of mass higher education systems and equity programs to create significant inroads into the social stratification of higher education, the limitations of national data collection and databases, and the challenges for reconceptualizing equity in a massified, globalized, higher education environment.

Annakodi and Indu (2014) conducted a study on teachers' attitude towards curriculum change in the implementation

ABSTRACT

Equitable Education System was proposed in the state of Tamil Nadu. It was felt that by following this education system we could afford impartial education to all school children irrespective of region such as rural and urban, upper and lower caste, and religion etc. This new system of education came into existence after a lot of oppositions, obstacles and confusions. Determining attitude and efforts to advance a new system of education is very much essential. Attitude of teachers, students and parents about a new educational system influences the choices and national development. Teachers and parents have a supreme responsibility in the mental and physical growth of the students. Their attitude is one of the most important variables in the education of children. Successful and effective implementation of a new system of education depends upon the knowledge of teachers and their positive attitudes towards it. Thus, the study of teachers' attitude towards Equitable Education becomes indispensable to the implementation plans. These observations initiated the investigator to undertake the present study, "*Attitude of Secondary School Teachers towards Equitable Education in Coimbatore District*"

Keywords: Attitude towards Equitable Education

INTRODUCTION

Education is the major 'life-process' of an individual. As there are certain indispensable vital processes of life in biological sense, so do education may be considered as a vital process in social sense. Education is indispensable to normal living. Without education, the individual would be found unqualified for growing

stage. This study investigates the attitude of teachers towards equitable education which was recently implemented in the state of Tamil Nadu in India. Two hundred and fifty four experienced teachers participated in the study. Data were gathered using Teachers Attitude Scale towards Equitable Education (TASEE), a rating scale constructed by the investigators. The statistical analysis of data revealed that majority of the teachers possess moderate attitude towards equitable education and it was also seen that teachers of government aided schools were having a favourable attitude towards equitable education.

METHOD OF THE STUDY

The present study attempts to find out the attitude towards equitable education of secondary school. Since the problem is concerned with "Survey" type, the investigator has selected the normative survey method for conducting the study.

The word 'survey' indicates the gathering of the data regarding current conditions. The word "normative" is used because surveys are frequently made for the purpose of ascertaining which is the normal or typical condition or practice. "**Normative Survey**" is applied in order to suggest the two closely related aspects of study. The descriptive or normative survey method of educational research is very

common. It is that method of investigation which attempts to describe and interpret what exists at present in the form of conditions, practices, processes in the form of conditions, practices, processes, attitudes, beliefs etc. It is concerned with the phenomena that are typical of the normal conditions. It is an organized attempt to analyze, interpret, report the present status of social institution, group or area.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Nine schools are selected through stratified random sampling technique. The sample for the present study consisted of 150 secondary school teachers in Coimbatore district. The teachers of both sexes coming from both rural and urban areas were included in the study.

TOOL USED IN THE STUDY

The data are essential for carrying out research investigation. The data are collected with the help of the special apparatus called as tools. The success of a research must be received by selecting a proper tool for the research. So, that the investigator used the following tool i.e. attitude towards equitable education.

DATA COLLECTION

In Coimbatore district, the investigator selected three government schools, three government aided schools and three self-financed schools using stratified random sampling technique. A set of management students from each school was selected in a random manner. Thus the researcher used stratified random sampling technique for collection of data from the vast area of Coimbatore district.

THE STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used in the interpretation of the data to draw to a more meaningful picture of results from the collected data in the present study from the following statistical measures were used.

- Mean
- Standard deviation
- 'T' test
- 'F' test

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. It is found that, there is a significant difference between male and female teachers of secondary school level in respect of their attitude towards equitable education.
2. It is found that, there is no significant difference between below 10 years and above 10 years teaching experience teachers of secondary school level in respect of their attitude towards equitable education.
3. It is found that, there is no significant difference between married and unmarried teachers of secondary school level in respect of their attitude towards equitable education.
4. It is found that, there is no significant difference between types of management of secondary school level teachers in respect of their attitude towards equitable education.
5. It is found that, there is no significant difference between rural and urban area teachers of secondary school level in respect of their attitude towards equitable education.
6. It is found that, there is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family teachers of secondary school level in respect of their attitude towards equitable education s.
7. It is found that, there is no significant difference between below Rs.10000 and above Rs.10000 monthly

income of secondary school level teachers in respect of their attitude towards equitable education.

CONCLUSION

The highest performing education systems are those that combine quality with equity. Equity in education means that personal or social circumstances such as gender, ethnic origin or family background, are not obstacles to achieving educational potential (definition of fairness) and that all individuals reach at least a basic minimum level of skills (definition of inclusion). In these education systems, the vast majority of students have the opportunity to attain high-level skills, regardless of their own personal and socio-economic circumstances. One of the most efficient educational strategies for governments is to invest early and all the way up to upper secondary. Governments can prevent school failure and reduce dropout using two parallel approaches: eliminating education policies and practices that hinder equity; and targeting low performing disadvantaged schools. But education policies need to be aligned with other government policies, such as housing or welfare, to ensure student success. The quality of education is not only with the quality of syllabus, but also about good educational environment, infrastructure, and quality teachers. The uniform education in Tamilnadu got its final shape after getting the view of eminent educationists. In addition to these, few matriculation private schools may teach some additional subjects like Hindi, French, German, etc. Uniform education doesn't mean to restrict one's pace in the field of education; its only aim is to maintain standard and quality in education. Thus, all the schools have to work hand in hand in achieving this laudable attainment. Different emphases laid in the four systems of school education need to be unified to lay a firm foundation for further education, successful careers and multi-faceted life.

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